

Rescuing the National Body? The Role and Imaginary of Maritime Lifesaving in the Nazi State

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The Deutsche Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger (DGzRS) is a German maritime rescue organization founded in 1865 and based on humanitarian principles to save shipwrecked persons regardless of nationality or other characteristics. Rather than stagnating or being disbanded during the Nazi period, the society expanded significantly, with a sharp increase in membership. It branded itself—visually and semantically—as a Nazi organization. Analysis of historical publications of the DGzRS and holdings in the German federal archives reveals how a humanitarian organization like the DGzRS could thrive under a fascist regime. This development was made possible because maritime lifesaving not only served a certain function for the Nazi state, which was amplified within the context of the Second World War, but also because idioms of rescue resonated with the social imaginaries of both humanitarianism and Nazism.

La Deutsche Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger (DGzRS) est une organisation allemande de sauvetage maritime fondée en 1865 et basée sur des principes humanitaires pour sauver les naufragés sans distinction de nationalité ou d'autres caractéristiques. Au lieu de stagner ou d'être dissoute pendant la période nazie, la société s'est développée de manière considérable, avec une forte augmentation du nombre de ses membres. Elle se présentait — visuellement et sémantiquement — comme une organisation nazie. L'analyse des publications historiques de la DGzRS et des fonds provenant des archives fédérales allemandes montre comment une organisation humanitaire comme la DGzRS a pu prospérer sous un régime fasciste. Une telle évolution fut rendue possible non seulement parce que le sauvetage maritime remplissait une certaine fonction pour l'État nazi, amplifiée dans le

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contexte de la Seconde Guerre mondiale, mais aussi parce que les idiomes liés au sauvetage entraient en résonance avec les imaginaires sociaux de l'humanitarisme et du nazisme.

AN EARLY, INTEGRAL PART of the Western humanitarian tradition was the imperative to save people from drowning in emergency situations such as shipwreck. Germany saw the creation of its own voluntary sea rescue society, the Deutsche Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger (DGzRS), in 1865. Rather than stagnating or being disbanded under Nazi rule, the organization underwent unprecedented technological modernization and its membership grew rapidly. It branded itself—visually and semantically—as a Nazi organization. How are we to explain the thriving of this humanitarian organization under a fascist regime? Humanitarianism, as it emerged between the mid-eighteenth and mid-nineteenth centuries, including the cause of saving people from drowning and/or shipwreck, was based on the universalist notion of a shared humanity, a common moral community, and a commitment to uphold the well-being and dignity of all individuals, irrespective of qualities such as race, nationality, or religion.¹ In contrast, in what the Nazis regarded as their morality, there was ultimately no responsibility to anyone who was outside the boundaries of the collective group, the racially defined *Volksgemeinschaft* (national community).² As Aurel Kolnai explained in 1938 in one of the first thorough political-philosophical analyses of Nazism, “The nation as the ultimate standard of its own conduct” was “the moral charter” of Nazi Germany. In Adolf Hitler’s view, Kolnai argued, humanitarianism was merely an “aesthetical obligation,” which was overridden by the needs of the nation, the latter supposedly being in a permanent struggle for existence.³ In a similar vein, the legal ideologist of the Third Reich, Carl Schmitt, notoriously claimed that “whoever invokes humanity wants to cheat.” According to him, states that invoked “liberal-individualistic” humanitarian objectives were doing so to “usurp a universal concept” to ultimately justify anything without limits from inhumane wars to economic imperialism, hence first and foremost furthering their own interests.⁴ These views also guided the Third Reich’s social and welfare policies, which focused on the care of the people (*Volkspflege*) rather than on the individual deserving of aid.⁵ Was the DGzRS, an organization whose purpose

1 Daniel Laqua, “Inside the Humanitarian Cloud: Causes and Motivations to Help Friends and Strangers,” *Journal of Modern European History*, vol. 12, no. 2 (2014), pp. 175–185; and Didier Fassin, *Humanitarian Reason: A Moral History of the Present* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2011), p. 252.

2 Rolf Zimmermann, “Holocaust und Holodomor. Was lehrt historische Erfahrung über Moral?” [Holocaust and Holodomor. What does historical experience teach us about morality?], in Werner Konitzer and Raphael Gross, eds., *Moralität des Bösen: Ethik und nationalsozialistische Verbrechen* [The morality of evil: Ethics and Nazi crimes] (Frankfurt: Campus Verlag, 2009), pp. 13–29, 18.

3 Aurel Kolnai, *The War against the West* (New York: Viking Press, 1938), pp. 30, 178.

4 Carl Schmitt, *The Concept of the Political* (1932; Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2007), p. 54.

5 Hans-Uwe Otto and Heinz Sünker, “Nationalsozialismus, Volksgemeinschaftsideologie und Soziale Arbeit” [National Socialism, the ideology of the national community and social work], in Hans-Uwe Otto and Heinz Sünker, eds., *Soziale Arbeit und Faschismus: Volkspflege und Pädagogik im Nationalsozialismus* [Social Work and Fascism: Care of the people and pedagogy in National Socialism] (Bielefeld: KT-Verlag, 1986),

was often described as fighting “a struggle for the existence of others,” not an anomaly in the context of the alleged permanent struggle for the existence of Nazi Germany?⁶ Or, perhaps, does this historical example caution us to be wary of such a strict dichotomy? Should we be more critical toward the universalist rhetoric of humanitarian organizations and examine their mechanisms of both inclusion *and* exclusion, since they devote their work in fact to “single issues”—in this case the issue of coastal lifesaving?⁷

In the decades following the Second World War, the DGzRS grappled with the assessment of its role in the Nazi period. On the occasion of its centennial, a self-commissioned history book claimed that the DGzRS had managed to “survive the whole dark era of a thousand years of glory like an untouched island of old bourgeois-humanitarian spirit and action: a heroic achievement in itself.”⁸ More recent self-assessments have been more nuanced. A 125th anniversary publication claimed that while the DGzRS was able to maintain its independence—“as far as circumstances allowed”—it did not exist in a vacuum: “As a rescue organisation supported exclusively by the people, it was also a reflection of the social conditions and forces in the country at all times.” The 140th anniversary book struck a similar note when it asserted that “there were probably all of them in the ranks of the DGzRS—the convinced, the followers, the quiet ones, the sceptics, the distanced ones, perhaps even one or another resistance fighter; simply a reflection of social conditions.”⁹ All these authors tried to judge the organization by evaluating the individual responsibility of the various echelons of the organization. One asserted that there were stories of DGzRS lifeboat crews not only rescuing enemy combatants (which is documented) but also helping individuals fleeing the Nazi regime to reach ships on open waters (which is not).¹⁰ To be sure, unlike other humanitarian organizations that played a role in Nazi Germany—such as the German Red Cross (Deutsches Rotes Kreuz [DRK]) or the German Lifesaving Society (Deutsche Lebensrettungsgesellschaft [DLRG]), concerned with questions of drowning and

pp. xiii–xxxvi, xxii; Christoph Sachße and Florian Tennstedt, *Der Wohlfahrtsstaat im Nationalsozialismus* [The Welfare State under National Socialism] (Stuttgart: W. Kohlhammer, 1992), p. 53.

- 6 The quote “Kampf um das Dasein Anderer” [struggle for the existence of others] with regard to the DGzRS, can be found, for example, in Ludwig Kemmer, “Die Ausbreitung der Deutschen Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger in Süddeutschland” [The growth of the DGzRS in southern Germany], *Beilage zur Allgemeinen Zeitung* [Supplement to the newspaper “Allgemeine Zeitung”], February 9, 1901; and in “75 Jahre Rettungswerk an deutschen Küsten” [75 years of rescue work on German coasts], *Deutsche Schifffahrts-Zeitschrift Hansa* [German shipping magazine Hansa], May 25, 1940. All translations of quoted material from the original German to English are the author’s.
- 7 On the inherent tension between universal humanitarian normativity and the particularism required to advance “single issues,” see Henning Trüper, “Aphrodite Stillborn: Heinrich Heine, Humanitarian Imperatives, and the Dead of Shipwreck,” *History of the Present*, vol. 9, no. 1 (2019), pp. 27–54. On the tension between universal humanitarian ideas and differentiating practices based on economic or political limitations, see Norbert Götz, Georgina Brewis, and Steffen Werther, *Humanitarianism in the Modern World: The Moral Economy of Famine Relief* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020), p. 16.
- 8 Hans Wirz, *Seenot, Opfer, Siege: ein Jahrhundert Deutsche Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger* [Distress at sea, sacrifices, victories: a century of the DGzRS] (Bremen: C. Schünemann, 1965), p. 244.
- 9 Peter Neumann, *DGzRS: 140 Jahre—140 Gedanken* [DGzRS: 140 years—140 thoughts] (Hamburg: DSV-Verlag, 2005), p. 140.
- 10 Bernd Anders, Andreas Lubkowitz, and Hermann Wende, *See-Not-Rettung: 125 Jahre Deutsche Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger* [Sea-Distress-Rescue: 125 years of the DGzRS] (Hamburg: Verlagshaus Die Barque, 1990), p. 119.

resuscitation)—the DGzRS was neither institutionally connected to the SS nor thematically entangled with issues of racial hygiene and eugenics.¹¹ However, investigating issues of individual responsibility would be a historiographical undertaking quite different from the one proposed in this article. Moreover, it would be a difficult task, since the archives stored at the DGzRS's headquarters in Bremen were first damaged by a fire during air raids in 1944 and then destroyed by a flood in 1946.¹²

Based on historical publications of the DGzRS and state documents preserved in several German archives, this article focuses instead on the question of what the DGzRS and its mission *meant* to the Nazi state and how the DGzRS conceived of its role in it. With the seizure of power by the Nazi Party, German civil society underwent a dramatic transformation. As part of Germany's *Gleichschaltung*, the reorientation of all organizations within the state and society according to Nazi principles, social and humanitarian organizations were dissolved if they were not ideologically aligned or politically useful to the Nazi state, or otherwise incorporated into the state apparatus. A number of organizations were created within the scope of the NS-Volkswohlfahrt (NSV), which embodied the Nazi understanding of welfare, which was about aiding and socially engineering the German people.¹³ If, in this situation, the DGzRS claimed to have maintained a certain degree of apparent independence, this was because the DGzRS, as a volunteer maritime rescue organization, gained a particular significance in Nazi Germany, which went beyond the traditional utility of maritime rescue societies to states. The first was the practical role that the DGzRS played in the naval and air operations of the Second World War. In this context, it was crucial to operate with neutral lifeboats that could be protected by the Geneva Conventions.

The second, more subtle significance of the DGzRS was that it could serve as an example of the self-proclaimed moral virtues of the social imaginary of Nazism. Social imaginary, as Charles Taylor has notably conceptualized it, is "something broader and deeper" than just ideas. He used the concept to analyze how people understand the moral order in which they live, namely "the ways people imagine their social existence, how they fit together with others, how things go on between them and their fellows, the expectations that are normally met, and the deeper

11 The DRK is the best-studied example as its collaboration was the most significant betrayal of its humanitarian values, its president swearing unconditional support to the Führer in May 1933, its vice-president (and Reichsarzt SS) and other members being active perpetrators of the euthanasia program and medical experiments, and the organization altogether embellishing the situation in concentration camps. Birgitt Morgenbrod, Stephanie Merkenich, and Hans Mommsen, *Das Deutsche Rote Kreuz unter der NS-Diktatur 1933–1945* [The German Red Cross under the Nazi dictatorship 1933–1945] (Paderborn: Ferdinand Schöningh, 2008). A critical history of the DLRG during the Nazi period remains to be written. For an informative "corporate history," see *Deutsche Lebens-Rettungs-Gesellschaft: 100 Jahre ehrenamtliches Engagement für die Gesellschaft* [The German Lifesaving Society: 100 years of voluntary work for society] (Bad Nenndorf: DLRG, 2013).

12 Neumann, *DGzRS*, p. 175.

13 Daniel Hadwiger, *Nationale Solidarität und ihre Grenzen: Die deutsche "Nationalsozialistische Volkswohlfahrt" und der französische "Secours national" im Zweiten Weltkrieg* [National solidarity and its limits: The German "National Socialist People's Welfare" and the French "Secours national" in the Second World War] (Stuttgart: Franz Steiner Verlag, 2021).

normative notions and images that underlie these expectations.”¹⁴ As Craig Calhoun argued, the social imaginaries of humanitarian emergencies in particular have two dimensions. One is the imaginary of those affected by the emergency, the victims of an earthquake or shipwreck, for example, who experience an exception to some kind of normal order. The other one relates to the humanitarian response, which is usually based on the idea of a common humanity or the idea of neutrality, among other moral norms.¹⁵ This social imaginary has a long history and has developed since the emergence of humanitarianism. Central to this imaginary also was, and is, the idea of an emergency constituted by the suffering of someone in need of urgent rescue. As this article argues, it was this idea of rescue in high-risk emergency situations that appealed to the Nazi imaginary, because it allowed for the display of virtues that the Nazis chose to promote as positive characteristics of their *Volksgemeinschaft*, such as heroism, self-sacrifice, and leadership. Moreover, the preservation of life in states of emergency was a constitutive element in the Nazi conception of state sovereignty. Visual and discursive analogies between the rescue mission of the DGzRS and the “rescue” of Nazi Germany were frequent and intensified as the lifeboat organization effectively participated in the “saving of Germany” through its work in search and rescue operations of the war.

This case study also illustrates what can happen to a humanitarian organization in a totalitarian, fascist system if it is not dissolved. What became (and what was left) of older humanitarian organizations *under* the Nazi regime (as opposed to the bulk of humanitarian activity that assisted the victims *of* the Nazi state, mostly from abroad) and how their structures, functions, principles, and imaginaries disintegrated or were integrated into the state apparatus has, with a few exceptions, remained under-researched.¹⁶

From a Liberal Nineteenth-Century Humanitarian Organization to a Rescue Organization of the Nazi State

The Origins of the German Lifesaving Movement

Most histories of Western humanitarianism begin with the gradual emergence, sometime between the mid-eighteenth and mid-nineteenth centuries, of a new sensibility toward the suffering of other human beings and the expression of sympathy for them in a variety of situations, guided by a variety of motivations.¹⁷ Whether it be toward the victims of earthquakes, the victims of slavery in the context of the abolitionist movement, or the wounded soldiers lying uncared for on the battlefield as the concern of the Red Cross movement, a moral duty developed by which the pain of others, even distant strangers, became intolerable and had to be

¹⁴ Charles Taylor, *Modern Social Imaginaries* (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2004), p. 23.

¹⁵ Craig Calhoun, “The Idea of Emergency: Humanitarian Action and Global (Dis)Order,” in Didier Fassin and Mariella Pandolfi, eds., *Contemporary States of Emergency: The Politics of Military and Humanitarian Interventions* (New York: Zone Books, 2010), pp. 29–58.

¹⁶ Exceptions are Hadwiger, *Nationale Solidarität*; and Morgenbrod, Merkenich, and Mommsen, *Deutsche Rote Kreuz*.

¹⁷ Silvia Salvatici, *A History of Humanitarianism, 1755–1989: In the Name of Others* (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2019), pp. 15–52; and Michael Barnett, *Empire of Humanity: A History of Humanitarianism* (Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2011), pp. 1–56.

addressed. This mutual obligation existed for the sole reason that both saviour and victim were human. Central to this understanding was thus the concept of humanity, which meant both a belonging to the same species that needed to be protected at all costs (thus a biological dimension) and a “humaneness” with which fellow members of this species needed to be protected. According to Didier Fassin, it is from these two dimensions—that every life is equally sacred and all suffering deserves to be alleviated—that the double meaning of humanitarian government to this day can be derived, namely that it is “a politics of life and a politics of suffering.”¹⁸

While some humanitarian causes concerned themselves with questions of structural injustice, many focused primarily on palliative solutions to alleviate suffering and save lives. One cause that embodied this basic, direct saving of lives like few others was the rescue of shipwrecked persons at sea. Like other humanitarian causes, it demanded a radical break with the moral norms of the past. Until then, modes of risk management had been mostly concerned with saving material goods, not lives. As far as coastal populations were concerned, a fatalist attitude coupled with a lack of resources, poverty, and perhaps the occasional prospect of profit through stranded goods kept them from organizing forms of rescue. In any case, promoters of maritime lifesaving introduced the humanitarian imperative to rescue the shipwrecked to coastal populations.¹⁹

Supporters of the cause organized themselves first into local and then into national volunteer organizations. While the first national lifesaving society was founded in Great Britain following the publication of an influential pamphlet by Sir William Hillary in 1823 (Royal National Lifeboat Institution [RNLI]), the moral change described above is also well illustrated by the creation of the German lifeboat society. Two shipwrecks on the East Frisian Islands, of the migrant ship *Johanne* in 1854 and the brig *Alliance* in 1860, raised awareness of the lack of organized structures of rescue. In both cases, the local population resigned itself to being onlookers unwilling or unable to come to the aid of the drowning passengers and crews.²⁰ Several appeals in the press soon led to the creation of local lifeboat societies, but the formation of larger structures was complicated by the fact that the German coast was divided among several states that had not yet been unified. Local societies were formed in Emden, Hamburg, and Bremen, but they refused to join the project for an all-German lifeboat society proposed by the Bremen Chamber of Commerce. It was largely thanks to the efforts of Arwed Emminghaus of the Bremen society that the various factions were brought together at a “unification assembly” on May 29, 1865, and the DGzRS was founded—six years before the unification of the German nation-state.²¹

18 Fassin, *Humanitarian Reason*, p. 248.

19 Henning Trüper, “Save Their Souls: Historical Teleology Goes to Sea in Nineteenth-Century Europe,” in Henning Trüper, Dipesh Chakrabarty, and Sanjay Subrahmanyam, eds., *Historical Teleologies in the Modern World* (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2015), pp. 117–142.

20 Hermann Sauerland, “Das Rettungswesen an der See” [Sea rescue services], *Veröffentlichungen aus dem Gebiete des Marine-Sanitätswesens* [Publications in the field of naval medicine], vol. 26 (1935), pp. 36–92.

21 Sven Claußen, *Die Seenotretter: 150 Jahre DGzRS* [The sea rescuers: 150 years of the DGzRS] (Erfurt: Sutton Verlag, 2015), pp. 56–57.

Nineteenth-century efforts to save the shipwrecked may have been led mostly by private humanitarian entrepreneurs and functioned through donations and voluntary labour, but the ambition to become nationwide rescue services made organizations reliant on the recognition, cooperation and support of the state in which they wished to operate. In the context of a biopolitical turn, European state administrations gradually recognized the utility of such national maritime rescue organizations. This is what Michel Foucault observed when he argued that since the eighteenth century, new technologies of power have been devised to preserve human life: Instead of an older approach to sovereignty based on the power of the state to threaten its population with death, the state now assumed a responsibility for the lives of its subjects, thereby gaining power over their bodies.²² Statisticians, national economists, and physicians discovered the utility of the individual body for the good of the state. Humanitarianism, as a “politics of life,” was a movement that could easily align itself with these objectives and argue and act accordingly. Humane societies, concerned with resuscitating the drowned, for example, reasoned that drowning could have a negative impact on society and the state by depriving businesses of valuable labour and leaving widows and descendants dependant on support.²³ Maritime lifesaving organizations used similar arguments. In his pamphlets, the founder of the RNLI, Hillary, emphasized the benefits that his institution would bring to the naval and commercial interests of the British Empire.²⁴ The fact that Bremen’s shipowners and merchants were involved in the founding of the DGzRS—and subsequent financial support, especially in times of ebbing donations—is yet another example of the commercial value that was frequently attached to organized lifesaving.²⁵

The volunteer lifeboatmen of maritime rescue societies, who risked their lives simultaneously for the good of humanity *and* the nation, became in this context part of the nineteenth-century Western imaginary as virtuous, patriotic, dutiful, heroic, and for the most part male figures comparable to soldiers fighting for their country.²⁶ As Bertrand Taithe has summarized, this period saw the formation of humanitarian masculine identities through “rhetorical devices and narrative tropes centered on risk-taking, on exposure to danger and even on sacrifice.”²⁷ DGzRS

22 For Foucault’s understanding of sovereignty, see Banu Bargu, “Sovereignty,” in John Nale and Leonard Lawlor, eds., *The Cambridge Foucault Lexicon* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), pp. 456–465. One important reference in Foucault’s work on this issue is Michel Foucault, *Il faut défendre la société : cours au Collège de France, 1975-1976* (Paris: Gallimard/Seuil, 1997).

23 Craig Barclay, “‘Our Heroes of To-Day’: The Royal Humane Society and the Creation of Heroes in Victorian Britain,” in Simon Wendt, ed., *Extraordinary Ordinarity: Everyday Heroism in the United States, Germany, and Britain, 1800–2015* (Frankfurt: Campus Verlag, 2016), pp. 25–53, 27.

24 William Hillary, *An Appeal to the British Nation on the Humanity and Policy of Forming a National Institution, for the Preservation of Lives and Property from Shipwreck* (London: G. and W. B. Whittaker, 1823), p. 6.

25 Wirz, *Seenot, Opfer, Siegf*, p. 194.

26 This phenomenon has been studied for several European countries. For France, see Frédéric Caille, *La figure du sauveteur. Naissance du citoyen secourateur en France, 1780-1914* (Rennes: Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2006); for Britain, see John Price, *Everyday Heroism: Victorian Constructions of the Heroic Civilian* (London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2014); for a *regard croisé* of Britain, Germany, and the United States, see Simon Wendt, ed., *Extraordinary Ordinarity*.

27 Bertrand Taithe, “Humanitarian Masculinity: Desire, Character and Heroics, 1876–2018,” in Esther Möller, Johannes Paulmann, and Katharina Stomig, eds., *Gendering Global Humanitarianism in the*

publications were full of such tales of heroism, which helped the organization successfully promote its cause. In addition to efficiently organized publicity, from the start there was a high degree of national identification through the patronage of the society by the German emperor and the honorary presidency assumed by maritime-minded members of the German imperial family. Moreover, during the period of accelerated German naval construction following 1897, the pervasive question of Germany's future naval capabilities also shaped the DGzRS's self-perception, leading to occasional collaborations with the navy.²⁸ The "single issue" of coastal lifesaving in Germany, albeit part of a transnational movement with a universal humanitarian claim, thus became entangled on several levels with the DGzRS's particular national requirements in order to thrive.

The society thrived to the extent that by 1885, it operated over 120 stations with more than a thousand lifeboatmen. By 1900, the society had about 53,000 members. However, the society suffered from a drastic drop in membership during and after the First World War (34,000 in 1915; 23,142 in 1933). The membership decline of the coastal rescue society could be explained first by switching humanitarian priorities during the war—in which the DGzRS only marginally took part given that fighting was primarily on the high seas—and second by the catastrophic economic situation after the war. The DGzRS was hit hard by a loss of value in its financial reserves due to high inflation.²⁹

Gleichschaltung and the Engineering of the Nazi Charity Market

In this difficult situation, the DGzRS leadership at least publicly shared the *Aufbruchstimmung*, a spirit of new beginnings, that pervaded large parts of the population when the Nazis came to power with the appointment of Hitler as chancellor on January 30, 1933. In 1933, the society's yearbook began with a full page of favourable political commentary by the Executive Committee: "Our report is under the auspicious star of Germany's national rebirth," it wrote. Regarding the appointment of the new "strong-willed" Führer, the committee claimed that no one could have welcomed these new developments more "joyfully" than their society.³⁰ Despite these public declarations, Gleichschaltung was not immediate. Early intrigues by low-level Nazi functionaries to replace members of the DGzRS staff and executive committee with party affiliates were initially fended off by the DGzRS leadership. At the same time, the latter was also proactive in aligning itself publicly with the new rulers. In a speech on July 28, 1933, DGzRS executive Adalbert Korff gave a radio speech in which he put Germany's former black, white,

Twentieth Century: Practice, Politics and the Power of Representation (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2020), pp. 35–59, 37.

28 Supporters of German naval policy, however, were better served by joining the German Navy League (*Flottenverein*) than the DGzRS. Christian Ostersehlte, *Die Deutsche Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger* [The German Sea Rescue Society] (Hamburg: E. Kabel, 1990), pp. 54–56.

29 Ostersehlte, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, pp. 30–31; Clayton Evans, *Rescue at Sea: An International History of Lifesaving, Coastal Rescue Craft and Organisations* (London: Conway Maritime Press, 2003), p. 223; Bundesarchiv Berlin Lichterfelde (German federal archives; hereafter BA), R2/23367, Reichsverkehrsministerium (Ministry of Transport; hereafter RVM) to Reichsfinanzministerium (Ministry of Finance; hereafter RFM), March 22, 1933.

30 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1932* [Yearbook 1932] (Bremen: DGzRS, 1933), pp. 1–3.

and red flag, the swastika and the symbol of the DGzRS on a single level. By 1935, the swastika flag was placed next to the DGzRS flag in publicity materials and henceforth became part of the society's self-representation (Figure 1). A delegation of the paramilitary Sturmabteilung (SA) took part in the 70th anniversary celebrations in spring 1935, in which "Sieg Heil" was shouted and the National Socialist German Workers' Party (NSDAP) anthem, "Horst Wessel Lied," was played.³¹

Figure 1. A donation box in the shape of a ship (Sammelschiffchen) showing a swastika flag alongside the DGzRS flag, 1936.

Source: DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1935* [Yearbook 1935] (Bremen: DGzRS, 1936), p. 21.

Beyond allegiance and symbolism, the new political regime also changed the society's structure within the scope of Gleichschaltung—although the changes were felt less than in other humanitarian organizations such as the DRK. By order of the Ministry of Transport, the German shipping industry was restructured according to the *Führerprinzip*, the principle according to which all orders of the Führer and his substitutes on lower levels of the various hierarchies of state and society had to be followed blindly and undemocratically. The industry was led by a *Spitzenvertretung* headed by the Hamburg shipowner John T. Essberger, to which DGzRS executive

³¹ DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1935* [Yearbook 1935] (Bremen: DGzRS, 1936), p. 21; Osterslehte, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, pp. 59–61.

Korff and his deputy were also appointed. The chairman of the DGzRS was no longer democratically elected by the board of trustees but rather appointed by Essberger. District branches (*Bezirksvereine*) were rebranded as *Ortsgruppen* (local groups; which was a semantic alignment with the Nazi regime). Essberger was a high-ranking NS functionary, and his shipping factory was an “NS model business,” but Jewish relatives and uncertain connections to resistance circles made him vulnerable. He seems to have been invested in keeping party influence in German commercial shipping to a minimum, and there is also no indication he attempted to further nazify the DGzRS.³²

While historian Christian Ostersehltte has convincingly argued that the DGzRS leadership did not include particularly staunch ideologues and even a few individuals who were known to disagree with Nazi ideology, this was hardly visible from the outside.³³ In 1935, Hitler not only agreed to become the patron of the DGzRS (the only “independent” voluntary organization for which he chose to assume this role) but also received a delegation from the DGzRS. On this occasion, Hitler expressed his support for the work of the DGzRS by purportedly saying that “voluntarily risking one’s own life to save others is not only a national, but in the highest sense a national socialist act that must be supported in every way.” This support could henceforth be used to leverage previously uninterested donors. Indeed, shortly after the meeting, the DGzRS emphasized in a request for support to the Deutsche Gemeindetag, the umbrella organization of all German municipal communities, that the DGzRS was acting “in the spirit of National Socialism.”³⁴ The same quote was used by Major Heinrich von Sybel, head of the DGzRS Berlin branch, when he solicited financial support from Propaganda Minister Joseph Goebbels.³⁵ The DGzRS leadership referred to its association with the Führer where it could, from letterheads to the yearbook. Its 1940 issue mentioned a number of high-ranking congratulators, including Hitler, and depicted him shaking hands with a lifeboatman at the rescue station of Horumersiel.³⁶ The Führer was repeatedly mentioned as having expressed his thanks and acknowledgements to DGzRS rescue crews.³⁷ The only request that Hitler refused to the rescue society was to have a lifeboat named after him (presumably wary of the image that would emerge if such a boat sank), but he did donate a large rescue motorboat in 1937 named the Hindenburg, which was indeed the first to sink in the war, after possibly hitting a mine off the island of Borkum in 1940, killing all six lifeboatmen on board.³⁸

32 Ostersehltte, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 61; Svante Domizlaff, *John T. Essberger: eine deutsche Geschichte der Tankschiffahrt* [John T. Essberger: A German history of tanker shipping] (Hamburg: Koehlers Verlagsgesellschaft, 1999), pp. 79–96.

33 Ostersehltte, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, pp. 60–61.

34 BA, R36/1263, DGzRS to Deutscher Gemeindetag, November 1935, and other documents in the same folder.

35 BA, R55/750, Sybel (DGzRS BV Berlin) to Goebbels, August 21, 1937.

36 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1940* [Yearbook 1940] (Bremen: DGzRS, 1941), p. 8.

37 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1939* [Yearbook 1939] (Bremen: DGzRS, 1940), p. 4.

38 BA, R5/1914, Bericht über den Verlust des Motorrettungsbootes “HINDENBURG” der Rettungsstation Borkum [Report on the loss of the motor lifeboat “HINDENBURG” at the Borkum rescue station], November 28–29, 1940.

Patronage of humanitarian organizations by heads of state has been a widespread practice since the nineteenth century and has always been more than symbolic, as patrons set an example and encouraged support and donations. In the case of Hitler, however, the uniqueness of his patronage for this cause (as opposed to a variety of other possible causes he could have chosen), the large amount of his donations (which constituted in themselves a form of state subsidy),³⁹ and the fact that donating to charity was often not a free decision in the Nazi state (Hitler's patronage and donations probably led some to believe that they were expected to donate as well) make this patronage stand out. The list of donors in the DGzRS yearbooks reads like a Who's Who of the Nazi state and included most of its ministers, such as Hermann Göring, Heinrich Himmler, and Baldur von Schirach, as well as several regional party leaders (*Gauleiter*). Hitler's support must have had a cumulative effect, as evidenced by a request for a donation made by the Berlin branch of the DGzRS to Goebbels. His ministry noted internally that such donations did not normally fall within its purview, but that because the DGzRS had such broad support throughout the Nazi political leadership, the money could be used for this purpose under the heading of domestic propaganda.⁴⁰

The close alignment of the DGzRS with the Nazi state was not exceptional. Welfare and longstanding independent humanitarian activities were heavily centralized and regulated under the Nazi regime. In many cases, these organizations and their activities became instruments of social engineering to shape, organize, and control the population at the national level as the regime saw fit. A functioning welfare system also legitimized the regime in times of political change and war and demonstrated the existence of a national form of solidarity. Most of the humanitarian or welfare organizations that existed under the Nazi regime were semi-state organizations that presented themselves as private organizations and primarily executed the social policies of the Nazi regime, i.e., measures to exclude politically or racially undesirable segments of the population. They were also important implementers of Nazi propaganda. This policy of exclusion—with the exception of the ubiquitous exclusion of Jewish members—did not apply to the DGzRS as it did to other NS welfare organizations, which distributed confiscated property and gradually excluded Jewish recipients from the distribution of any kind of welfare. As far as can be told from the sources, it continued to carry out its rescue operations indiscriminately.⁴¹

However, the DGzRS's revenue increase and its record-high membership under the Nazi regime raise questions. In fact, humanitarian organizations that did not

39 For example, in 1939, Hitler donated a combined sum of RM 60,000 (as a rough indicator, this is worth over US \$400,000 in 2024, as measured by inflating the amount by the Consumer Price Index, calculated with the help of <https://www.measuringworth.com/>. The same method has been used for other amounts cited in this article). In 1940, Hitler bestowed a jubilee gift of RM 250,000 in addition to his regular donation of RM 10,000. In 1941, he again donated a combined sum of RM 60,000, by far the highest donation (individuals never donated more than RM 3000; NSV gave RM 6000). DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1939*, p. 43; DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1941* [Yearbook 1941] (Bremen: DGzRS, 1942), p. 16; BA, R43-II/559, Korff to Hitler, March 20, 1940.

40 BA, R55/750, Reichsministerium für Volksaufklärung und Propaganda (Ministry of Public Enlightenment and Propaganda; hereafter RMVP), internal memorandum, November 14, 1938.

41 Hadwiger, *Nationale Solidarität*, pp. 14–17.

agree with the political priorities or ideology of the Nazi regime were restricted and financially starved.⁴² As of November 1934, the collection of public donations required special permission from the Ministry of the Interior (granted annually to only about 15 organizations for certain periods of the year, including the DGzRS, whose number was reduced to three in 1937). The official justification for this restriction was that the “generosity and sense of sacrifice” of the population should not be abused for purposes that were not in the interest of the Volksgemeinschaft. Beginning in September 1939, the public collection of donations for charitable purposes, which did not relate to war-related priorities, was prohibited. Exceptions were granted during the war years only to ideologically aligned organizations and organizations of importance for the war effort and the expansion of the Reich such as the DRK, the Reichsverband für Deutsche Jugendherbergen (Reich Association for German Youth Hostels) or the Volksbund für das Deutschtum im Ausland (Association for Germanism Abroad).⁴³ The DGzRS was one of these organizations. While the permission was revoked in September 1939 with the outbreak of the war, it was reinstated with certain restrictions in January 1940 until the end of the war.⁴⁴ Support also came in the form of direct government subsidies, starting in March 1933, when the Ministry of Transport granted a sum of RM 600,000 (retroactively for the years 1929–1932),⁴⁵ for a reconstruction program and building of new lifeboats.⁴⁶ Simultaneously, membership numbers also took off. Unlike the First World War, which had seen a dramatic decline, the Second World War saw a sharp increase.⁴⁷ Membership reached an unprecedented high of 220,000 in 1943.⁴⁸

In contrast, while the DGzRS thrived, many other relief organizations were dissolved altogether and their property transferred to the NSV or the DRK. Ultimately, the war was used as an argument to demand “imperiously the concentration and unified control of all the forces and resources of the German people.”⁴⁹ The left-wing Arbeiter-Samariter-Bund, for example, was one of the first to be dissolved in the summer of 1933, and most of its assets were given to the DRK.⁵⁰ The DRK

42 See, for example, the deliberate starving out of the Salvation Army for ideological reasons: BA, R43-II/559, Pfundtner (Reichministerium des Innern, Ministry of the Interior; hereafter RMI) to Chef der Reichskanzlei (Reich Chancellery), March 26, 1938.

43 BA, R43-II/559, Reichsschatzmeister NSDAP to RMI, March 8, 1941, and other correspondence in same folder; Paul Schoen, “Geschichte, Selbstanspruch und Stellenwert der Nationalsozialistischen Volkswohlfahrt NSV 1933–1939” [History, self-expectation, and significance of the National Socialist People’s Welfare (NSV) 1933–1939], in Otto and Sünker, *Soziale Arbeit und Faschismus*, pp. 199–220, 217.

44 The last proof is from February 1944, BA, R5/1915, RMI to DGzRS, February 9, 1944.

45 Roughly worth over US \$4 million in 2024 as measured by inflating the amount by the Consumer Price Index.

46 BA, R2/3367, RVM to RFM, March 22, 1933.

47 BA, R5/1914, Bericht über die Tätigkeiten des Bezirks-Vereins Berlin der DGzRS [Report on the activities of the Berlin district branch of the DGzRS], 1940.

48 Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, pp. 33–35.

49 See for example BA, R43-II/559, Vollzug des Sammlungsgesetzes [Execution of the law for collections] November 5, 1934; Lockerung des Sammelverbots zugunsten des Winterhilfswerks [Relaxation of the collection ban in favour of the winter relief organisation], January 8, 1940; Frick to the deputy of the Führer and others, January 16, 1937; Quote from letter from Dr. Stuckart to RMI and Chef der Reichskanzlei, February 7, 1940.

50 Daniel-Erasmus Khan, *Das Rote Kreuz: Geschichte einer humanitären Weltbewegung* [The Red Cross: History of a global humanitarian movement] (München: Beck, 2013), p. 83.

itself, however, was also gradually reoriented to its original purpose of assistance in times of war starting in the same year; its welfare program was completely abolished and transferred to the NSV in 1937.⁵¹ Many donations to Nazi-approved campaigns such as the annual *Winterhilfswerk* (Winter Relief Campaign) were voluntary in name only, not private, and were often collected under pressure. The rationale for framing collections as donations rather than welfare taxes was to “educate” the people to make sacrifices in the spirit of self-help—and only (seemingly) voluntary giving could be considered sacrificial. Donating became altogether a sacrificial ritual through which the individual reaffirmed his or her belonging to the community of the people.⁵²

The rise of the DGzRS thus coincided with an ideologically motivated transformation and shrinking of the charity market. These changes apparently provided the DGzRS with competitive advantages. While other humanitarian organizations were dissolved or reduced in size, the DGzRS, although it remained officially a voluntary, nonpartisan and nongovernmental organization, retained the right to collect donations within certain limits and benefited from expressions of support from the highest-ranking Nazis, from the Führer on down. The importance of donations for public purposes in Nazi Germany, the ideological orientation of the DGzRS and its reach into the Navy and the Wehrmacht, especially with the outbreak of the war, coupled with a professionalized public relations organization and strategy (as will be shown below), all seem to be factors that explain the thriving and strong increase in membership of the DGzRS during the Nazi period. And the DGzRS knew how to use its regained popularity. The requests that the DGzRS made to authorities to receive preferential treatment over other humanitarian organizations (such as the right to collect donations) reveal what role the DGzRS attributed to itself in the Nazi state: it emphasized the importance of its work in terms of educating the population through “selflessness and heroism,” as well as its growing importance for future defence and war-related tasks.⁵³ The following sections analyze these two functions.

The Militarization of Lifesaving

Shipwrecks often occur in the context of political violence, be it in relation to colonial exploitation, the fortification of maritime borders against migrants or, as in this case, a war of annihilation.⁵⁴ The DGzRS made it clear from the beginning that it supported this war ideologically. Its 1940 yearbook praised as “gigantic” the “tremendous military successes” of the armed forces, “victorious in all theatres of operations and on all fronts,” and was enthusiastic about “the most fateful battle

⁵¹ Morgenbrod, Merkenich, and Mommsen, *Deutsche Rote Kreuz*, pp. 38, 137–138.

⁵² Sachße and Tennstedt, *Der Wohlfahrtsstaat*, pp. 124–125; Ralf Banken, *Hitlers Steuerstaat: Die Steuerpolitik im Dritten Reich* [Hitler’s tax state: Tax policy in the Third Reich] (Berlin: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2018), pp. 380–389.

⁵³ BA, R43-II/559, DGzRS BV Berlin to Chef der Präsidialkanzlei des Führers und Reichskanzlers (Head of the Presidential Chancellery of the Führer and Reich Chancellor), February 8, 1940.

⁵⁴ Johannes F. Lehmann, *Die Strategie der Rettung: Geschichte und Gegenwart eines machtpolitischen konzepts* [The strategy of rescue: History and present of a power-political concept] (Stuttgart: S. Hirzel Verlag, 2024), pp. 29–30.

of all time” allegedly forced upon Germany by Great Britain. In that year, the DGzRS was still assured that, “thanks to the bold deeds and successes of navy and air force,” Germany’s coasts were not “covered by an uninterrupted graveyard of wrecks of sunken ships, as is the case around England”; but the fighting soon reached Germany’s coasts—in contrast to the First World War, when fighting at sea took place beyond the DGzRS’s reach.⁵⁵ By the second year of the war, combat operations had shifted to the North Sea, and German and Allied fighter planes were being shot down over water. Although the Luftwaffe’s sea rescue service had search planes, they were usually only able to drop rescue equipment and could not provide immediate assistance, especially in rough seas. As early as 1939, therefore, the DGzRS signed an agreement with the Wehrmacht that placed it under the joint authority of the Reich Aviation Ministry and the High Command of the Navy. The society then took over the Special Coastal Rescue Service (Sondereinsatz der Küstenrettungsboote), which began operations in the spring of 1940.⁵⁶

Due to the unprecedented role of the DGzRS in the war, very different from the society’s marginal involvement in the first world conflict, there was initial confusion about the institutional, financial, and legal aspects of the DGzRS’s role in the German war effort. Its exact role was eventually agreed upon at a meeting on November 5, 1941, at the Aviation Ministry between representatives of the DGzRS and representatives of all interested parties from the relevant German ministries and the affected branches of the armed forces. It was agreed that for the duration of the war, the High Command of the Navy would be responsible for personnel and material matters, while the Sea Emergency Center (Seenotzentrale Nord) in Wilhelmshaven would be responsible for the operational side of the rescue boats. The latter, in cooperation with the DGzRS, would draw up new operating instructions.⁵⁷

The question of whether lifeboats were protected by the Geneva Convention was debated among various German authorities, between the government and the DGzRS, and between the belligerents. At first their status of protection was unclear, since lifeboats were not hospital ships in the traditional sense, and the British authorities feared a strategic advantage for Germany if they agreed to extend protection to lifeboats.⁵⁸ The DGzRS was of the opinion that its boats were entitled to protection, or at least to be allowed to display the Red Cross symbol, since it had concluded an agreement with the DRK to set up Red Cross “stations” on its boats, manned by a DRK worker, in order to be able to provide better first aid to the wounded.⁵⁹ In the end, the High Command of the Navy came to the conclusion that the Red Cross symbol should be displayed depending on whether a lifeboat was carrying military personnel or members of the Red Cross, even if it did not

55 Quotes from DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1940*, p. 3.

56 Claußen, *Die Seenotretter*, p. 73; Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 45.

57 BA, R5/1914, Ergebnis der Besprechung im Reichsluftministerium (Aviation Ministry; hereafter RLU), November 5, 1941.

58 See documents on British views on the question; for example, in the Kew National Archives, Records of the Admiralty, Naval Forces, Royal Marines, Coastguard, and related bodies, ADM 1/10454, and Air Ministry and Ministry of Defence: Registered Files, AIR 2/8106.

59 BA, R5/1914, Von Alten (DGzRS BV Berlin) to RVM, January 18, 1940.

warrant protection.⁶⁰ This decision suggests that the lifeboats were occasionally used for purposes not directly related to the DGzRS's humanitarian mission; but the DGzRS was ordered not to publish any reports on its wartime operations, and if it had, it would not have published anything even remotely critical, so this is difficult to verify.⁶¹

In addition to their legal protection, the DGzRS's constant involvement in the war posed difficult practical challenges for its rescue crews, who had to navigate in rough seas and between mines, with no sea markings or lights, and the risk of being mistakenly fired upon.⁶² Rather than being launched from shore, the lifeboats were often stationed in open water where they could respond to an alarm via wireless telegraph or telephone, and were sent to coordinates based on a system of designated "accident squares."⁶³ Most lifeboatmen must have been unacquainted with this militarized environment, as many of them were pursuing civilian professions alongside their volunteer lives.⁶⁴

In order for the DGzRS and its crews to be able to fulfill these tasks and for its infrastructure to meet the requirements of the war, the organization underwent an unprecedented state-funded modernization program, which included the construction of new rescue stations and boats and was classified as being of the highest priority for the war effort (*höchste Dringlichkeitsstufe S*).⁶⁵ This allowed for rapid construction despite the scarcity of such materials as metals. Despite these approvals, the difficulty of finding certain components repeatedly delayed production.⁶⁶ In order to meet the set targets, the DGzRS received large sums from the Ministry of Transport for the construction of new rescue stations and boats.⁶⁷ The *Großbauprogramm* of 1941 included the building of 36 new rescue boats of three different types, but the final course of the war meant that only half of them were delivered. Nevertheless, the war ended for the DGzRS with a highly developed technical apparatus.⁶⁸ This reflected, albeit on a much smaller scale, the speed with which Nazi Germany had also built up its naval fleet since May 1938 and the fact

60 BA, R5/1914, Korff to RVM, February 16, 1940; Memorandum B. Nr. A/H M V 467/40, Oberbefehlshaber der Kriegsmarine [Supreme navy commander] (signed Wesemann), January 24, 1940.

61 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1940*, p. 12.

62 Hans Georg Prager, *Retter ohne Ruhm: das Abenteuer der Seenothilfe* [Rescuer without glory: The adventure of lifesaving at sea] (Berlin: Ullstein, 1999), pp. 150–152.

63 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1940*, p. 5.

64 While still volunteers, the crews were gradually professionalized since the founding of the DGzRS through rescue and first aid training. Some particularly demanding jobs such as machinist or foremen were progressively converted into salaried positions during the interwar period. Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 51.

65 Rescue stations were built at Norderney, Dorumer Tief and Ordung. BA, R5/1914, Minutes of the results of a meeting at the RLU, November 5, 1941; Von Alten (BV Berlin) to RVM, December 27, 1939; RVM to Reichshauptkasse, February 19, 1940.

66 BA, R5/1915, DGZRS to RVM, June 29, 1942.

67 Between 1939 and 1941, the DGzRS received combined subsidies of RM 3,310,000 (roughly worth over US \$28 million in 2024, adjusting for inflation). BA, R5/1914, Vorstand DGzRS to RVM, January 26, 1942.

68 BA, R5/1914, Vorstand DGzRS to RVM, September 5, 1941; Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 46.

that it was able to produce more technologically advanced war equipment in 1944 than it could in 1940.⁶⁹

As the previous two sections have shown, humanitarian organizations, if they were not dissolved as ideologically inconvenient, underwent processes of nationalization and militarization. This was true of the DGzRS as well as for other organizations such as the DRK or the NSV, the latter of which played an important role in dealing with the consequences of air raids, for example. This humanitarianism was a counter-model to concepts of bourgeois international solidarity as embodied by movements such as the International Red Cross.⁷⁰ Of course, the DGzRS emerged precisely from that internationalist bourgeois humanitarian tradition, which was concerned with the suffering of strangers. In fact, the lifesaving movement had a longstanding tradition of international exchange between national organizations. While operational collaborations at sea were limited (but occurred occasionally, for example, with the Dutch Noord- en Zuid-Hollandsche Redding-Maatschappij throughout the 1930s), the DGzRS proactively cultivated bilateral and multilateral relations through correspondence, the exchange of technical expertise and material, as well as visits with other lifesaving societies, in particular in Britain, France, and the Netherlands, since the nineteenth century. From its creation, the DGzRS also participated in international exchanges such as world exhibitions and international congresses on accident prevention and, since 1928, in the international Lifeboat Conference (first organized in London in 1924 on the initiative of the RNLi), the regular gathering of the International Lifeboat Federation. Such international cooperation came to a standstill for the German society with the start of the war, unless it concerned the cultivation of ties with the sister organizations of allied states such as the Romanian rescue society, which the DGzRS advised. The international Lifeboat Conference, which Germany was supposed to host in 1940, was cancelled as well due to the war. Germany was also not officially invited to the first conference after the war in 1947 in Oslo.⁷¹ Despite its isolation within the movement, the DGzRS nevertheless stuck to its initial values of indiscriminate aid to the shipwrecked when during the war it rescued 1,626 people from different warring parties.⁷² In the case of the DGzRS, the Nazi authorities chose not only to tolerate, but even to encourage these values of solidarity, because they were useful to the regime in several ways. Not only did it see the organization as militarily relevant, but it also considered the organization more generally as being tied to Germany's supposed naval identity and standing. The following sections explore this dimension further by looking at three types of interrelated imaginaries: heroism, the saving of the body, and the saving of the German nation.

69 Michael Salewski, "Die Deutsche Kriegsmarine zwischen Landesverteidigung und Seemachtambitionen" [The German Navy between national defence and naval power ambitions], in Michael Salewski, Jürgen Elvert, and Stefan Lippert, eds., *Die Deutschen und die See: Studien zur deutschen Marinegeschichte de 19. und 20. Jahrhunderts* [The Germans and the sea: Studies in German naval history in the 19th and 20th centuries] (Stuttgart: F. Steiner, 1998), pp. 191–198, 195–198.

70 Hadwiger, *Nationale Solidarität*, p. 20.

71 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1939*, p. 6; Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, pp. 95–109.

72 Prager, *Retter ohne Ruhm*, p. 151.

Rescue in the Nazi Imaginary

Sacrificial Heroes and Führers

During the interwar period, the publicity work of humanitarian organizations gradually became more professional, using newly available audio and visual technologies to reach potential donors. In 1935, for example, the UFA (Universum Film AG) produced a film exclusively for the DGzRS, a version of which was used in schools.⁷³ In 1938, the DGzRS also benefited from the support of public radio for advertisement such as from the Reichssender Hamburg and Bremen.⁷⁴ In 1939, merchandise was introduced. It was also in the mid-1930s that a fully remunerated employee was hired to centralize this public relations work.⁷⁵ The DGzRS was thus well aware of the image that it had to project in order to attract new members.

Social science literature on humanitarianism has shown how humanitarian NGOs, in their attempt to persuade others of their worthiness through media strategies, have “crafted a language that resonates with the international community.”⁷⁶ This makes sense if, as Didier Fassin argued, the liberal “humanitarian reason” has become an integral part of the social imaginary of modern Western society.⁷⁷ In the Nazi regime, however, any reference to entities beyond the state was usually to be avoided. The dominant resonance for persuading donors came through the Nazi social imaginary.

Through public statements we know what role and image Nazi ideologues attributed to lifesaving and the DGzRS. I have already mentioned Hitler’s statement on the DGzRS. Another poignant example was a commemorative book published on the occasion of the DGzRS’s 70th anniversary in 1935. The book contained signed congratulatory messages by high-ranking functionaries of the Nazi state (or whatever official wrote the statements on their behalf) such as the Führer’s deputy, Rudolf Heß, Propaganda Minister Goebbels, or Prussian Prime Minister Göring, among others. Heß, for instance, emphasized the “courage, risk of life, and constant willingness to make sacrifices” of the lifeboatmen, which were “the same ideals to which the National Socialist movement owes its success.” Göring, too, lauded the “willingness to make sacrifices” as being part of “German manhood” (*Opferbereitschaft ist deutsche Mannesart*).⁷⁸ In a similar vein, the Mayor of the city of Bremen, Otto Heider, considered the DGzRS lifeboatmen to be putting into practice a “National Socialism of Action” (*Nationalsozialismus der Tat*) as exemplified by a “German sense of sacrifice” (*Opfersinn*), which was central to the Nazi understanding of welfare.⁷⁹ Under no circumstances could the Führer be associated with “Gefühlsduselei” (a pejorative term vaguely translatable as

⁷³ Ostersehlte, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 35.

⁷⁴ DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1939*, p. 8.

⁷⁵ Ostersehlte, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, pp. 32–33.

⁷⁶ D. Robert Dechaine, “Humanitarian Space and the Social Imaginary: Médecins Sans Frontières/Doctors Without Borders and the Rhetoric of Global Community,” *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, vol. 26, no. 4 (2002), pp. 354–369, 357.

⁷⁷ Fassin, *Humanitarian Reason*, p. 247.

⁷⁸ DGzRS, *70 Jahre Seerettungswerk der Deutschen Gesellschaft zur Rettung Schiffbrüchiger* [70 years of sea rescue work of the DGzRS] (Oldenburg/Berlin: Stalling, 1935), p. 5.

⁷⁹ DGzRS, *70 Jahre Seerettungswerk*, p. 10.

sentimentalism) and a cause in which people did not strive to help and sacrifice themselves—in this case through volunteerism in risk-prone situations.⁸⁰

What all these statements have in common is a recourse to imaginaries and metaphors of war, which, as explained above, had been in use since the nineteenth century in relation to the figure of the rescuer but easily found a place in the Nazi imaginary: The lifeboatmen fought like soldiers and sacrificed themselves to save the shipwrecked victim from drowning in a fight against the pitiless element of the sea.⁸¹ But the Nazi imaginary elevated them to new heights, given how central ideas of fighting and death were to it—and a reality in the Second World War. As the best-known analyst of the language of the Third Reich, Victor Klemperer has described military-style heroism in Nazi society as ubiquitous and pervasive. Its tropes were applied to any context in which someone could be regarded as willingly risking their lives, such as race car drivers or army tank drivers. Therefore, it is unsurprising that the tradition of humanitarian risk-taking among lifeboatmen appealed to the Nazi imaginary.⁸² Here, the nuance that the heroism initially claimed for itself by the DGzRS was a “quiet heroism” for the sake of humanity was only superficially relevant.

Moreover, the dangerous maritime environment was a suitable place to illustrate the idea of the leader. As mentioned earlier, the Führer principle was applied to the DGzRS as it was to other organizations of the Nazi state. This meant that the organization was subject to the unconditional authority of the Führer. Besides, as Hannah Arendt argued, the principle also meant that any other leader of the system was “his walking embodiment” and was just carrying out the supreme leader’s orders.⁸³ If Hitler was also seen as the “saviour of the German people,” which was supposedly threatened by all sorts of imminent dangers and therefore depended on his leadership for its very existence, the situation of rescue at sea suggested itself as analogous.⁸⁴ In an emergency at sea, the rescue crew was usually composed of volunteers who in their regular lives might have been leaders themselves (such as captains or pilots). In this situation, however, they were led by one coxswain or “foreman” (in German, *Vormann*, a neologism reflecting the tradition that lifeboats did not have a proper captain), who not only had authority over them, but who—at least when rowed boats were in use—was literally the only one looking forward while the others were rowing.

80 Hadwiger, *Nationale Solidarität*, pp. 147–159.

81 Lehmann, *Strategie der Rettung*, p. 160.

82 Victor Klemperer, *LTI. Notizbuch eines Philologen* [The Language of the Third Reich] (Berlin: Aufbau-Verlag, 1947), p. 15.

83 Hannah Arendt, *The Origins of Totalitarianism* (London: Penguin Classics, 2017), p. 477.

84 Klemperer, *LTI*, pp. 53–57.

Figure 2. Cover of the 1940 yearbook of the DGzRS depicting a rescue boat with crew and a rescue plane above within the scope of the Special Coastal Rescue Service (Sondereinsatz der Küstenrettungsboote).

Source: DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1940* (Bremen: DGzRS, 1941).

One propaganda artist of the Third Reich, Günther-Lothar Buchheim, who would become famous decades later as the author of the novel *Das Boot* (The boat), described in his Nazi-era article “Kämpfer zu See” (Fighters at sea) the particular way in which the maritime context lent itself well to the Nazi imaginary of the “fearless Führer” with its combination of factors such as “the force of human dedication,” “the proximity of machines,” “the unfathomably eerie water,” and “the breathtaking power over dead matter.”⁸⁵ The more the DGzRS became involved in the war itself, the more its descriptions resembled those of the Buchheimian propaganda imagery. “In the confined space of the small craft, the men on these boats performed a grueling service that demanded the utmost vigilance, energy and commitment, in the fight against not only the destructive forces of the sea but also the ever-lurking danger of modern weapons and combat methods on and under the water and in the air,” the 1941 yearbook read.⁸⁶ The stout lifeboatmen in their thick oily raincoats and life jackets (Figure 3) hardly resembled the ideal of the smooth, edgy Wehrmacht soldiers depicted in Nazi propaganda, but both could be used to convey a certain idea of masculinity and heroism. In this case, masculinity was defined by the devotion to a higher cause and a voluntary form of camaraderie rather than by physical features.⁸⁷ In fact, the depiction of groups of soldiers on boats was also a popular trope.⁸⁸ It is not difficult to see how a dynamically forward-moving crew—be they soldiers or lifeboatmen—would have been perceived, by a contemporary audience, as embodying the German Volksgemeinschaft with the foreman as their leader, the Führer. The cover of the 1940 yearbook (Figure 2) showed such a boat belonging to the sea rescue service together with a rescue plane above and the accident squares in the background that guided the crew to the coordinates of an emergency.

Saving the Body of the People

There is thus a mixing, in the imaginary conveyed by the DGzRS publications, of the rescuing of the body of the shipwrecked and the body of the people. Political philosopher Claude Lefort has emphasized the importance of this body of the people in the imaginary of totalitarian regimes of different ideologies. According to him, the representation of the People-as-One, as opposed to the Other, constituted in these regimes a body to the head of the omnipotent power exercised by the leader, the *Egocrat*.⁸⁹ The DGzRS Executive Committee greeted the appointment of the leader

85 Quoted in Gerrit Reichert, *U 96—Realität und Mythos: der Alte und Lothar-Günther Buchheim* [U 96—Reality and myth: The Old Man and Lothar-Günther Buchheim] (Hamburg: Mittler, 2019), p. 115.

86 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1941*, p. 3.

87 George L. Mosse, *The Image of Man: The Creation of Modern Masculinity* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1996), pp. 155–159.

88 Wolfgang Schmidt, “Die Mobilisierung der Künste für den Krieg: Maler in Uniform” [Mobilizing the arts for war: Painters in uniform], in Hans-Jörg Czech and Nikola Doll, eds., *Kunst und Propaganda: im Streit der Nationen 1930–1945* [Art and propaganda: In the dispute between nations 1930–1945] (Dresden: Sandstein, 2007), pp. 284–297, 290–291.

89 Claude Lefort, “The Image of the Body and Totalitarianism,” in Claude Lefort and John B. Thompson, eds., *The Political Forms of Modern Society: Bureaucracy, Democracy, Totalitarianism* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1986), pp. 292–306, 300.

Hitler as chancellor as a “saving act” (*rettende Tat*) for Germany.⁹⁰ To be sure, the DGzRS continued to save individual bodies, but they accommodated themselves to the Nazi hierarchy that suggested that the body of the people came first, the body of the individual second. This view was consistent with the biopolitical interpretation of lifesaving, which, as suggested earlier, accompanied the emergence of lifesaving societies in the nineteenth century.

This outright biopolitical understanding of lifesaving suggested by the imaginary of the saving of the body of the people was illustrative of a more general politics of life that underpinned the Nazi state, as several political philosophers, from Emmanuel Levinas and Kolnai to Foucault and Giorgio Agamben, have pointed out. Kolnai devoted considerable thought to the “cult of ‘Life’ and ‘Nature’” on which the Nazi political system rested and which “placed the process of life above all objective necessities.” Levinas, similarly, in the early 1930s, affirmed the importance of the biological body as the centrepiece of the spiritual life of the Nazis with their emphasis on bloodlines and heredity.⁹¹ Foucault reaffirmed that there was no state in which biological life was taken care of more thoroughly than in the Nazi state. According to him, from procreation to the control of illnesses and accidents, there was no society that was more disciplinary and precautionary than the one projected by the Nazis. Hence, according to him, the control of hazards linked to “biological processes” was one of the main goals of the regime.⁹² The overarching objective of Nazi humanitarian, social welfare, or medical organizations was correspondingly not the rescue of the individual body but the rescue of the *Volkskörper*, the “biological body of the nation.”⁹³

Saving Germany

The extent to which the DGzRS imagined itself as being tied to the existence of Germany as a nation is illustrated by a certain repeated evocation of the mythical circumstances of its founding in the 1860s—it being a common practice of humanitarian practitioners to anchor their organization’s identity and legitimacy in the memory of mythological origin stories.⁹⁴ The fact that the DGzRS was founded at a time when the German nation had not yet been created and German states were still embroiled in wars was of importance to both the DGzRS and the Nazi leadership. Once again, a congratulatory message, written by Minister of the Interior Wilhelm Frick on the occasion of the society’s 70th anniversary in 1935, is informative. Frick, or the unnamed official who composed the text on his behalf,

90 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1932*, pp. 1–3.

91 Kolnai, *War against the West*, pp. 195, 220; Emmanuel Levinas, “Reflections on the Philosophy of Hitlerism (1934),” *Critical Inquiry*, vol. 17, no. 1 (1990), pp. 63–71.

92 Foucault, *Il faut défendre la société*, pp. 213–235.

93 Giorgio Agamben, *Sovereign Power and Bare Life* (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 1998), pp. 144–148. See also Hagen Markwardt, Fruzsina Müller, and Bettina Westfeld, “Einleitung” [Introduction], in Hagen Markwardt, Fruzsina Müller, and Bettina Westfeld, eds., *Konfession und Wohlfahrt im Nationalsozialismus: Beispiele aus Mittel- und Ostdeutschland* [Denomination and welfare under National Socialism: Examples from central and eastern Germany] (Berlin: Duncker & Humblot, 2021), p. 9.

94 Bertrand Taithe and John Borton, “History, Memory and ‘Lessons Learnt’ for Humanitarian Practitioners,” *European Review of History*, vol. 23, no. 1–2 (2016), pp. 210–224, 218.

explicitly drew a parallel between German unity and the DGzRS. He emphasized that the founding of the organization in 1865 took place at a time of the “worst state fragmentation” caused by dynastic interests of various German principalities in combination with a “lack of understanding of *völkisch* sentiment.” This division had not only been “animated by the feeling of purest humanity and noblest charity” but—recalling the above understanding of male heroism—had been, by the same token, “an act of stout-hearted masculinity and true patriotic self-determination.” To Frick, this was the expression of a more general feature of the German people. The fact that thousands of Germans from all regions and of different social standing felt it to be their “duty of honour” to make sacrifices to this cause was, in his view, a foreshadowing of the same “patriotic enthusiasm” that Germans always remembered in difficult times and that “found its long-awaited and highest satisfaction” with the union of the German people under Hitler.⁹⁵

This logic was essentially taken up by the DGzRS itself in a commemorative history published by the organization in 1940 on the occasion of its 75th anniversary. In the context of the self-inflicted threat of Germany by outside forces during the war, it made a comparison similar to Frick’s: “Here it was again, the unfortunate German fragmentation and jealousies, which then also seriously threatened [the founding of the DGzRS]!” At that time, too, the call for the creation of rescue services had to go to *all* Germans to succeed. The above-mentioned “struggle for unity” (*Der Kampf um die Einheit*) of the three different rescue societies was implicitly linked to the struggle for German unity. In fact, at the founding of the DGzRS, this link had been real, since several founders of the organization belonged to the same bourgeois national liberal milieu that was involved in the German revolution of 1848–1849, and who, after its political failure, turned to social causes.⁹⁶ The political imaginary of Nazism, however, was not interested in the struggle for a unified state with a constitution, rule of law, and a parliament, as associated with the 1848–1849 revolutions, but merely in the symbolism of pan-Germanic unification.⁹⁷ In the commemorative book of 1940, this symbolism was visually underpinned with contemporary depictions of lifeboatmen acting and rowing in unity (Figure 3). The fact that the Emperor of the German Reich assumed patronage of the DGzRS shortly after its creation reinforced the idea that the society was tied to the newly sovereign German Empire. And the fact that the leader of the Third Reich, Hitler, had agreed in 1935 to continue this tradition, the DGzRS claimed, had awakened the willingness of the population to stand behind the society’s rescue work.⁹⁸ It was therefore only coherent that, in 1933, the DGzRS told a very similar story about the

95 DGzRS, *70 Jahre Seerettungswerk*, p. 6.

96 Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 16.

97 For Nazi thinking on the revolution of 1848–1849, see Tobias Hirschmüller, “Die Revolution von 1848/1849 in völkischen Geschichtsbildern zwischen Kaiserreich und Nationalsozialismus” [The 1848/1849 revolution völkisch images between the German Empire and Nazism], in Julien Reitzenstein, Dirk Rupnow, and Bernd-A. Rusinek, eds., *Völkisches Denken 1848 bis 1948: Von der Paulskirche über Weimar zum Petersberg* [Völkisch thought 1848 to 1948: From the Paulskirche via Weimar to Petersberg] (Berlin: De Gruyter Oldenbourg, 2023), pp. 105–120, 112–118.

98 DGzRS, *Der Untergang des Seglers Johanna und die Entstehung des Rettungswerkes an der Küste* [The sinking of the sailing ship Johanna and the creation of the rescue service on the coast] (Berlin: Verlag Hoppenstedt, 1940), pp. 22–28, 32.

equivalence of the cause of German unity and of the establishment of a nationwide lifesaving service on the occasion of the “saving act” of Hitler being appointed Reichskanzler after “a period of severe internal struggle.”⁹⁹

Figure 3. Page from a 1940 commemorative book discussing the “struggle for unification” of the DGzRS in 1865 illustrated by the contemporary photograph of a rescue crew rowing in unison.

Source: DGzRS, *Der Untergang des Seglers Johanna und die Entstehung des Rettungswerkes an der Küste* [The sinking of the sailing ship Johanna and the creation of the rescue service on the coast] (Berlin: Verlag Hoppenstedt, 1940), pp. 22–23.

In the imaginary of Nazism, the existence of the DGzRS was also tied to Germany’s maritime role. In Goebbels’s words, for example, rescuing shipwrecked people was a “matter of the highest honour for every seafaring nation,” something of particular importance for a nation like Germany, which had “regained its honour after a deep fall.” There had always been a sense of national pride among the supporters of the DGzRS for having a nationwide rescue service. It was the “first truly patriotic German association,” recalled Emminghaus at the society’s 50-year celebration, which took place in the midst of the First World War. He claimed that the promotion of the lifesaving cause had not only done its bit to turn the thoughts of a large land-oriented nation toward its maritime interests; the existence of the DGzRS had also “freed Germany from a shortcoming that characterized it ingloriously

⁹⁹ DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1932*, pp. 1–3.

when other seafaring nations had long since taken appropriate measures to rescue shipwrecked persons.”¹⁰⁰

The DGzRS perceived the relative lack of interest of the German population in the decades after the First World War as devastating to its membership and donation numbers. It identified in what it regarded as a restored national unity under Hitler an opportunity to win back support in all parts of Germany.¹⁰¹ The newly gained support that they indeed received was, in addition to the changes of the charity market explained above, also linked to the expansive projects of the Third Reich, which extended to the maritime. For instance, in March 1939, the DGzRS requested to be able to collect donations from the newly annexed Ostmark, justifying the request with the high level of interest that it received from the newly annexed territory and its importance for German *Seegelung* (naval significance).¹⁰²

The idea of *Seegelung*, namely that Germany had a racially determined maritime destiny and a rightful place among seafaring nations and that there should be a concerted effort by all relevant parts of the German state—its military and merchant navy as well as the German population—to contribute to it, was, as of 1934, promoted by the Reichsbund Deutscher Seegelung headed by Vice-Admiral Adolf von Trotha.¹⁰³ The idea was not only to reconnect with some mythical past of Germanic seafarers and to make seafaring an integral part of German identity, but also to contribute, ultimately, to German *Weltgeltung*, meaning significance on the world stage, in the future.

In the early 1940s, some circles in the German navy envisaged a vast military and commercial fleet with its central port in a Germanized “Drontheim.” From there, an empire would be controlled stretching from the French coast to the Ural, with the Mediterranean essentially becoming a German inland sea and sub-Saharan Africa a large German colony.¹⁰⁴ For someone like von Trotha, the DGzRS rescuers were pioneers of this vision, its men “looking steadfastly out over the wide, eternally moving sea, where the freedom of the nation demands its right.” In his view, they were building up an “outpost line” on the German coasts and their heroic deeds “command the greatest respect in the world for the German name and German nautical prowess.”¹⁰⁵ In a voluminous 1942 compendium on the fundamentals of German *Seegelung*, an entire chapter was devoted to coastal lifesaving, along with chapters on issues such as colonization, navigation, tropical medicine, meteorology, ship safety, and salvage.¹⁰⁶ And between September 1941 and February 1942, the

100 DGzRS, *70 Jahre Seerettungswerk*, pp. 8–12.

101 DGzRS, *70 Jahre Seerettungswerk*, pp. 8–12.

102 Austrian State Archives (ÖStA), Zivilakten NS-Zeit [Civil files Nazi-period] 4351/17, Vorstand to RMI, March 3, 1939; RMI to the DGzRS, April 29, 1939.

103 Bendix von Barga, “Reichsbund deutscher Seegelung” [Reich association of German sea power], *Deutsche Schiffsfahrtszeitschrift Hansa* [German shipping magazine Hansa], vol. 71 (September 1934), pp. 1354–1357.

104 Michael Salewski, “Das maritime Dritte Reich” [The maritime Third Reich], in Salewski, Elvert, and Lippert, eds., *Die Deutschen und die See*, pp. 228–245.

105 DGzRS, *70 Jahre Seerettungswerk*, pp. 9–10.

106 The author of the chapter, a captain of the commercial navy, was affiliated with the DGzRS. Hans Berber-Credner, “Das deutsche Küstenrettungswesen” [The German sea rescue service], in Walter Lohmann, Ferdinand D. H. Dannmeyer, and Georg Lauritzen, eds., *Grundlagen Deutscher Seegelung* [Fundamentals of German naval significance] (Berlin: Verlag Wehrfront Alfred Becker, 1942), pp. 544–548.

DGzRS showcased its technical advancements in the field of maritime rescue at the exhibition *Großdeutschland und die See* (Greater Germany and the sea) organized by the Reichsbund Deutscher Seegelung at the German Museum in Munich.¹⁰⁷ Individual lifeboatmen may not have cared about these geopolitical schemes, but their connection to maritime rescue shows how in the minds of Nazi ideologues even the smallest cog served a greater purpose in advancing the greater cause and how interest for the DGzRS went hand in hand with a general interest in the maritime.

Conclusion

An analysis of the social imaginaries surrounding the DGzRS in the Nazi regime demonstrates that idioms of rescue, especially in their soteriological meaning, resonated not only with the tradition of humanitarianism but also with imaginary of the Third Reich. The Gleichschaltung of the DGzRS thus did not constitute a break with the rescue society's past or with the history of lifesaving in general. Rather, both humanitarian actors and the Nazi regime selectively picked out and amplified a limited number of pre-existing, aligning imaginaries to carve out a certain narrow, Nazi-compatible, and exclusive interpretation of humanitarianism. The "single issue" of German costal lifesaving lent itself well to such an adaptation and could evolve despite, or, rather, because other humanitarian issues on the German charity market were severely restricted.

In the male-dominated field of lifesaving, nineteenth-century ideas and practices of civic and soldierly heroism, part and parcel of the nineteenth-century humanitarian imaginary, corresponded to ideas of self-sacrifice, risk-taking, and devotional masculinity in the Nazi imaginary.¹⁰⁸ Similarly, Nazi notions of the salvation of the Volkskörper echoed earlier biopolitical and national-patriotic ideas about the purposes of lifesaving. The practice of patronage as adopted by Hitler was seen as being in the tradition with the monarchical patronage of German emperors and an expression of the sovereign's role as protector not only of charitable causes but also of the seas. Even references to universal "feelings of humanity" could occur as long as they were coupled with particular feelings of patriotism and self-sacrifice. Finally, the fact that the DGzRS was a voluntary maritime rescue organization with a specific place in German history allowed Nazi ideologues to draw comparisons between the rescue of Germany, allegedly threatened by external and internal forces, and the rescue of shipwrecked persons, threatened by the adversities of the sea. If we take a closer look at the DGzRS's strategy to recruit new members, for example, the society took into consideration this context of ruptures and continuities presented by the Nazi period and appealed to a combined sense of older charity (*Nächstenliebe*) and *völkisch* patriotism at the same time.¹⁰⁹ This transformation illustrates the possible coexistence of humanitarian imaginaries that can be both inclusive and exclusive.

¹⁰⁷ DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1941*, p. 8.

¹⁰⁸ As many of the society's 800 members were drafted to the front, in some cases their wives took over the business of the local branch, including collection of membership fees, but their work is rarely mentioned and entirely absent from the male-dominated imaginary.

¹⁰⁹ DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1939*, pp. 7, 39.

A popular book on the history of the DGzRS, first published in 1978, stated that the organization since its founding had “always remained true to itself and its humanitarian mission” and had “always been as modern as possible without ever falling victim to a cheap zeitgeist.”¹¹⁰ As this article demonstrates, this claim is both right and wrong. The rescue society managed to continue its mission during the Nazi regime, even in a more efficient and modern manner than before, but it only did so because it adapted to the Nazi imaginary and linked it to its tradition. It is not the intention of this article to cynically reduce the 160-year history of the DGzRS to the 12 years of Nazi rule. When the DGzRS celebrated its 75th anniversary in 1940, it could claim to have saved almost 6,000 lives, of which at least 2,997 were non-German.¹¹¹ In 2015, the DGzRS estimated that it had saved about 82,000 lives since its inception. Today, the DGzRS prides itself on having always upheld the core value of independence, alongside volunteerism, as a prerequisite for rescuers to go into action on a voluntary basis.¹¹² However, as this article has shown, this independence was not always a given. After all, it was only in 1957 that the DGzRS, which had been dependent on the state for its reconstruction efforts, decided to renounce any financial support from the state.¹¹³

After the war, the DGzRS did not take any time for self-reflection. The DGzRS asked all its members to destroy any documents referring to Hitler’s patronage. Beginning in 1950 with Theodor Heuss, who symbolized political renewal for many Germans, the patronage was taken over by West German presidents.¹¹⁴ Preoccupied with securing its own existence, the DGzRS, which in February 1948 was given permission by the Allied authorities to resume its activities,¹¹⁵ returned to a more factual style in its reports and demonstrated its *raison d’être* by assisting wrecked ships in the North and Baltic Seas. Many of these were small coastal freighters and fishing boats, which, as the DGzRS explained in a letter to its donors in 1948, contributed to the food supply and thus provided a service to the starving population.¹¹⁶ In these early post-war years, the lifeboat society, as it presented itself to the national public, thus continued to be concerned with *rescuing* the German population from the consequences of the war.

110 Prager, *Retter ohne Ruhm*, pp. 11–12.

111 DGzRS, *Jahresbericht 1939*, p. 49.

112 Claußen, *Die Seenotretter*, pp. 6–9.

113 Anders, Lubkowitz, and Wende, *See-Not-Rettung*, pp. 56–57.

114 Ostersehle, *Deutsche Gesellschaft*, p. 63.

115 Universitätsarchiv Freiburg (University Archives Freiburg; hereafter UAF), E0007/1698, Aus unserer Arbeit 1945/46 [On our work 1945/46], signed Hermann Helms Jr., May 1946. This was only true for the British occupation zone and later the FRG. In the GDR, in 1955, a separate lifesaving service was created first within the scope of the Red Cross then within the Seefahrtsamt (Maritime authority).

116 UAF, E0007/1698, Letter to donors by DGzRS, January 1, 1948.